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PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR DEVELOPING ECONOMIC THINKING IN STUDENTS BASED ON FOREIGN EXPERIENCE**Nishonova Dilafruz Komilovna***Teacher of the Department of General Education, New Age University**e-mail: dilafruzkomilova13@gmail.com*

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi asosida o'quvchilarda iqtisodiy tafakkurni rivojlantirishning pedagogik shart-sharoitlari tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda iqtisodiy ta'limning samaradorligini oshirishda ilg'or xorijiy ta'lim tizimlarining yondashuvlari, interfaol metodlar, loyihaviy va kompetensiyaga asoslangan ta'lim texnologiyalari o'rganilgan. Maqolada iqtisodiy tafakkurni shakllantirishda o'qituvchining kasbiy mahorati, o'quv muhitining motivatsion xususiyatlari hamda amaliy mashg'ulotlar va tadbirkorlik elementlarining o'rnini yoritilgan. Xulosa sifatida, xorij tajribasini milliy ta'lim tizimiga moslashtirish o'quvchilarning iqtisodiy tafakkurini rivojlantirishda muhim omil sifatida e'tirof etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: iqtisodiy tafakkur, xorij tajribasi, pedagogik shart-sharoitlar, iqtisodiy ta'lim, innovatsion metodlar, kompetensiyaga asoslangan yondashuv, ta'lim tizimi, o'quvchi faoliyati.

Abstract. This article analyzes the pedagogical conditions for the development of economic thinking in students based on the experience of foreign countries. The study examines the approaches of advanced foreign educational systems, interactive methods, project-based and competency-based educational technologies in increasing the effectiveness of economic education. The article highlights the role of the teacher's professional skills, motivational features of the educational environment, as well as practical exercises and entrepreneurial elements in the formation of economic thinking. In conclusion, the adaptation of foreign experience to the national education system is recognized as an important factor in the development of students' economic thinking. Keywords: economic thinking, foreign experience, pedagogical conditions, economic education, innovative methods, competency-based approach, education system, student activity.

Аннотация. В статье анализируются педагогические условия развития экономического мышления студентов на основе опыта зарубежных стран. В исследовании рассматриваются подходы передовых зарубежных образовательных систем, интерактивные методы, проектные и компетентностные образовательные технологии в повышении эффективности экономического образования. В статье освещается роль профессионального мастерства преподавателя, мотивационных особенностей образовательной среды, а также практических занятий и предпринимательских элементов в формировании экономического мышления. В заключение отмечается, что адаптация зарубежного опыта к отечественной системе образования признается важным фактором развития экономического мышления студентов.

Ключевые слова: экономическое мышление, зарубежный опыт, педагогические условия, экономическое образование, инновационные методы, компетентностный подход, система образования, активность студентов.

Introduction. In today's globalization and market economy, the development of the economic thinking of the younger generation is one of the priority tasks of the education system. Because economic thinking forms the financial literacy of students, the ability to analyze economic processes, approach them consciously and make the right decisions. The experience of developed countries shows that by creating special pedagogical conditions in the process of economic education and training, it is possible to expand the economic worldview of young people and prepare them for life.

Nowadays, the possession of economic knowledge and skills is becoming increasingly important not only in the personal life of each person, but also in the development of society. The economic thinking of a person is the ability to understand, analyze economic processes, make rational decisions and apply them in practical activities. The development of such thinking is, first of all, closely related to the pedagogical conditions created in the educational process.

In today's era of globalization, the correct organization of pedagogical conditions in the educational process requires the study of international experience. In developed countries, pedagogical conditions aimed at developing economic thinking are formed in different ways.

Pedagogical conditions are a set of organizational, methodological, psychological and practical factors necessary for the development of students' economic thinking in the educational process. Among them, aspects such as the richness of curricula, the use of modern pedagogical technologies, the involvement of students in practical activities, and the connection of economic knowledge with real life are of particular importance.

Studying this topic will allow us to determine which conditions will give the most effective results in the process of developing economic thinking, to implement them in the education system, and to form students as economically mature, responsible and entrepreneurial individuals. Therefore, the analysis of pedagogical conditions for the development of economic thinking is one of the current scientific and practical issues of our time. In addition, studying this through foreign experience will contribute to the globalization of research.

In particular, in European countries such as Germany, Great Britain, and Finland, economic subjects are an integral part of school programs and are aimed at developing practical knowledge and skills in students. In the USA, through project-based education and "school banks," students learn economic activity directly in practice. In Japan and South Korea, the development of economic thinking is combined with national values - the principles of thrift, honesty, and teamwork.

The study of these experiences is also relevant for the education system of Uzbekistan. Because in our country, in the process of modernization of the economy, development of entrepreneurship, and increasing financial literacy, it is important to educate the younger generation economically mature. Therefore, adapting foreign experiences to local conditions, improving pedagogical conditions, and applying innovative educational approaches are one of the urgent tasks of today.

Literature analysis. Many scientists have conducted research on foreign experiences of pedagogical conditions for the development of economic thinking in students. As a result, the possibilities of economic thinking in pedagogy have also

increased. This is reflected in the scientific views of such scientists as T.Yu. Gavrilenko and V.V. Kurenkov, among our country's scientists. The main views of scientists are as obvious as day, having conducted research on international experiences in the economics of continuing vocational education in Russia.

One of our domestic scientists, M.I. Nurmatova, also expresses her views on foreign experiences of pedagogical cooperation in the formation of economic competence of higher education students in her research. She also gives ideas on the formation and work processes of pedagogical technologies in the formation of economic education, the methodology for their effective use in the application of foreign experiences.

The CIS countries also have a high role in this regard. After all, the issues of forming an economic culture and developing economic thinking in them are constantly emerging as topical issues. The research of N.A. Kiseleva and other scientists reflects the results of foreign experience in the formation of student scientific societies.

In the conditions of rapid socio-economic development, globalization, informatization of the education system, the importance of scientific knowledge, the need for scientific personnel are increasing. The development of scientific knowledge, gaining experience in project and research activities from school is becoming a particularly important stage in the training of many specialists from various fields of science, economics and social spheres. Undoubtedly, the problems associated with the development of scientific knowledge, skills, qualifications and project-based research experience are not limited to universities. They are also very relevant in schools, technical schools and higher education and require the support of various social institutions.

Today, it is becoming clear that the active involvement of school, technical school and higher education students in scientific research and projects is not only an important feature of the educational process, but also a mandatory requirement in accordance with the updated state educational standards. In order to achieve the goal of developing the scientific knowledge of school, technical school and higher education students, the joint creation and interaction of motivated participants is very important.

Therefore, scientific teams of school, technical school and higher education students are especially effective in this regard. They provide students with wider opportunities for development and self-improvement through creativity and communication than is possible in the classroom.

In order to continue the literature review, M.B. Urazova and D.A. Jumayeva also conducted foreign experiences in the development of economic thinking. In particular, students put forward ideas, models and views on domestic and foreign models of the formation of project competence.

Research methodology. In conducting the research, methods such as scientific research, induction and deduction, expert assessment, observation, survey, modeling, systematization, comparison and comparison, analysis were used to reveal the true essence of the topic.

Analysis and results. In the educational system of foreign countries, special attention is paid to the development of economic thinking among students. Because in the global market environment, the financial literacy of the younger generation, their understanding of economic processes, and the ability to make informed decisions are important factors in the development of society.

First of all, the experience of European countries shows that the development of economic thinking is established from the initial stage of the education system. For example, in Germany, Finland and the UK, economic subjects are included as a separate module in school programs. Students learn economic concepts not theoretically, but through everyday life examples. Attention is paid to financial management, thrift, entrepreneurship and investment skills.

In the US experience, practical exercises and project-based learning are widely used in the development of economic thinking. "School Banking" programs have been introduced in schools, where students have the opportunity to try out processes such as small savings, loans, and investments in practice. This strengthens the financial decision-making skills of young people.

In Asian countries, in particular, in Japan and South Korea, the education of economic thinking is combined with national values. In schools, children are taught the principles of thrift, honesty, collective responsibility and efficiency in connection with economic subjects. Through this, not only economic knowledge, but also economic culture are formed in students.

The main conclusions from international experience are that effective pedagogical conditions for the development of economic thinking are:

- regular inclusion of economic subjects in curricula;
- linking economic knowledge with practical life situations;
- widespread use of project-based learning and interactive methods;
- ensuring cooperation between school and family;
- using digital educational resources and simulations;
- combining national values with economic education.

Thus, foreign experience shows that in the formation of economic thinking in students, it is important to combine theory and practice, use modern educational technologies, and be based on the integration of national and global values.

In conclusion, the formation of economic culture in students has wide pedagogical possibilities, and this process is carried out through a combination of systematic and continuous education, practical training, innovative methods and educational activities. In this way, students in the future will become economically conscious, able to make independent decisions, active and responsible individuals in society.

1. The theoretical foundations of teaching economic disciplines are considered a component of the system for training junior specialists, and this factor is of great importance in developing and improving the economic literacy characteristics of students of non-economic higher education institutions, educating them as competent specialists and perfecting them.

2. The relevance of the problem was proven during the course of conducting economic educational work with students of various colleges, developing a model created in the process of implementing the development of economic literacy, as well as criteria for assessing economic knowledge, skills and qualifications.

3. The results of the study showed that our hypothesis that all components of economic education and upbringing should be carried out in harmony and in connection with vocational education in the development of economic literacy in students is justified. Scientifically based methods for achieving economic literacy in practice have been created.

Pedagogical conditions for the development of economic thinking are a decisive factor in the formation of economic knowledge, skills and qualifications in students. The analysis shows that the use of effective methods and technologies in the educational process, linking economic knowledge with practice, and directing students to independent thinking and making economic decisions are among the most important conditions.

Also, adapting curricula to modern requirements, taking into account the age and psychological characteristics of students, and involving them in economic games, projects and entrepreneurial activities increases the effectiveness of the formation of economic thinking. The joint activities of the family, social environment and the pedagogical team also have a positive effect on this process.

In general, the creation of pedagogical conditions for the development of economic thinking serves to educate students as economically conscious, responsible and entrepreneurial individuals. This not only increases the efficiency of the education system, but also plays an important role in the development of society.

Foreign experience shows that in order for pedagogical conditions for the development of economic thinking to be effective:

- educational programs should be based on the harmony of theory and practice;
- wide use of modern pedagogical technologies;
- involvement of students in economic activities from a young age;
- taking into account national values and social traditions.

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